

Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Tomb, Ancestral Worship, Cantonese, Nationalism, Language, Mausoleum, Religious Place, Tomb, Sinitic, Religious Complex

The Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum was constructed in Nanjing from 1926 to 1929. Sun was an architect of his own memorial in the sense that he planned his political afterlife, strategizing to preserve his spiritual legacy and physical body as potent public icons. Sun Yat-sen instructed that his remains be preserved in the manner of the Russian leader Lenin whom he admired and that his tomb be located on Purple Mountain (Zijin shan 紫金山) near the tomb of the first Ming Emperor Hongwu (r. 1368–1398). The Mausoleum played a major role in the construction of the cult of Sun Yat-sen by the Nationalist government as part of its quest for political and ideological domination. It combined imperial conventions with modern emphases on the visual representation of political and ritual power. The Mausoleum played an important role in the creation of "Sun-ism," a political cult that portrays Sun Yat-sen as the founding father and the supreme leader of the nation, who embodied the quintessential Chineseness and the ability to lead the people to their salvation. Nationalist politicians, students, servicemembers, and members of social groups were expected to participate in commemorative rituals at the Mausoleum. Their visits were not only a demonstration of their loyalty to the state and the party but also an opportunity for them to be transformed into ideal citizens by the powerful spirit of the supreme leader.

Date Range: 1926 CE - 2024 CE

Region: Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum

Region tags: East Asia

Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum on Purple Mountain,
Nanjing

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Wang Liping. "Creating a National Symbol: The Sun Yat-sen Memorial in Nanjing." *Republican China* 21, no. 2 (1996): 23–63.
- Source 2: Lai, Delin. "Searching for a Modern Chinese Monument: The Design of the Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum in Nanjing." *Journal of the Society of Architectural Historians* 64, no. 1 (2005): 22–55.
- Source 3: Musgrove, Charles D. "Monumentality in Nanjing's Sun Yat-sen Memorial Park." *Southeast Review of Asian Studies* 29 (2007): 1–19.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://zschina.nanjing.gov.cn/>

– Source 1 Description: Official website of the Nanjing Zhongshan Cemetery Administration Bureau

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– No

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Type of elevation

– Mountain

Notes: The Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum is located on Purple Mountain (Zijin shan 紫金山) near the tomb of the first Ming Emperor Hongwu (r. 1368-1398).

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

– Clearing

– Trackway or road-surface

– Plantings

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Notes: The Mausoleum is located in the city of Nanjing, but up in the mountain away from the urbanized area.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– Yes

↳ Is there an established route of travel connecting it to a wider transportation network:

– Yes

Notes: Visitors can take the municipal metro line to get off at Xiamafang Station, and then walk about 15 minutes to get there.

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Mausoleum is located on the mountain. Visitors climb almost 400 stairs to reach the marble three-bay gate. The stairway is lined with pine, cypress, and ginkgo trees. At the end of the stairway is the Sacrificial Hall (some scholars translate it as Memorial Hall). Inside the hall lies the marble sarcophagus of Sun Yat-sen.

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

Notes: The Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum is a memorial complex. The main mausoleum where Sun's body is hosted was constructed from 1926, to 1929. The main architect was Lü Yanzhi, a Cornell University graduate who was employed by the firm of Henry K. Murphy (1877-1954). In the 1930s, the government also constructed the Public Cemetery for the Fallen Officers and Soldiers of the National Revolutionary Army to the left of the Mausoleum. Henry Murphy designed a memorial hall that provided a modern museum experience by showing visitors photographs and personal artifacts of fallen soldiers. Murphy also constructed the cemeterial grounds in three semicircles, mimicking the "armchair style" of southern Chinese tombs. The cemetery was adorned by Linggu Pagoda (Linggu ta 靈谷塔), a 175-foot reinforced concrete pagoda in Murphy's "adaptive" style.

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

Notes: Trees were planted alongside the stairway leading to the Mausoleum to create a "spirit path" (shendao), which was a commonly seen feature for Ming imperial tombs.

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

Notes: The Nationalist government created "a necropolis dedicated to the ancestors of modern Chinese nationalism," where visitors' thoughts could be enriched and transformed, by building facilities such as a memorial site with gardens, lakes, and pavilions, a memorial hall to house Sun's relics, a library of revolutionary history, and a Sun Yat-sen culture institute. In addition, the Mausoleum is located near the Hongwu Emperor's tomb. Meiling Place, was built for Soong Mei-ling, wife of Chiang Kaishek in 1934. The Purple Mountain Observatory was first built in 1934 by the Nationalist government. The Aviation Martyrs' Cemetery was built in 1932. Wang Jingwei's tomb was built in the 1940s but was destroyed after World War II. The Mausoleum is also part of the Purple Mountain where there are over 200 heritage and scenic sites are located. It served as the burial ground of officials since the Eastern Han.

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Notes: The Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum was designed to be a space large enough to accommodate 50,000 participants and a tomb that allowed viewing of the sarcophagus. This scheme had no precedent in Chinese architecture.

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: Although the Mausoleum was neglected during the early People's Republic era, it was not destroyed. However, the Nationalist emblems were removed or covered. Many inscriptions, except those of Sun's and his wife Song Qingling's, were erased. During the 1980s, the Mausoleum were repaired and restored. Parts of the original decorations (such as the Nationalist Party flag on the ceiling) were reconstructed.

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify

–Other [specify]: The government under the Chinese Nationalist Party (Guomindang)

Notes: The Nationalist leader Chiang Kai-shek initiated the project.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– No

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

Specify

– War/battle

Notes: The Mausoleum was planned prior to Sun Yat-sen's death in 1925. With the success of the Northern Expedition, a military campaign launched by the National Revolution Army under Chiang Kai-shek in the late 1920s, the Mausoleum was constructed.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– Yes

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Expression of devotion with no expectation of favor in return

Notes: Sun was an architect of his own memorial in the sense that he designed his hagiographic afterlife and strategized to preserve his spiritual legacy and physical body as potent public icons. The Mausoleum played a major role in the construction of the cult of Sun Yat-sen by the Nationalist government as part of its quest for political and ideological domination. It was part of the Nationalist Party's effort to create a monumental, ceremonial center of the new China in which the Party was the leader. It combined imperial conventions with modern emphases on the visual representation of political and ritual power.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Notes: It was built to house the sarcophagus of the founding father of modern China.

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: The structures were built on the Purple Mountain, which is the main landscape feature.

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: The Mausoleum combined the traditional imperial tomb with modern nationalist architecture. A stone three-bay gate marks as the entrance. A huge bronze vessel (ding) was installed to symbol political power. Hundreds of stairs lead to the Sacrificial Hall (jitang 祭堂). Inside the hall is the vault (mushi 墓室) where Sun's remains were kept.

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Notes: The vault is the highest and most sacred place as it houses the remains of Sun Yat-sen.

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The Mausoleum was an unprecedented monument in Chinese history. It was modeled after Lincoln Memorial and traditional Chinese architecture.

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 50

Notes: The Mausoleum complex is over 100 acres, and it is situated in the Scenic Area, which is surrounded by numerous trees.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 750

Notes: The Sacrificial Hall is about 30 meters in length and 25 meters in width.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 60

Notes: The Linggu Pagoda, as part of the Mausoleum complex, is 60 meter high. The Sacrificial Hall is 29 meters high.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 750

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 29

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand

– No

↳ Clay

– No

↳ Plaster

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– No

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Glass tiles

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– Yes [specify]: Reinforced Concrete

Notes: The Nationalist government wanted to build long-lasting structures. They avoided using bricks and wood as construction materials.

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

Notes: The ceiling of the Sacrificial Hall is decorated with the Republic of flag of white sun on a blue sky.

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: The ceilings of the Sacrificial Hall and the vault are particularly ornate, with the "white sun on the blue sky" flag and repeated red rectangle patterns. These symbolize the idea of "white sun, blue sky, and red earth." The Republic of China flag has this color scheme (red, white, and blue). There are six reliefs surrounding Sun's statue, with each depicting key events in Sun's revolutionary career.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction,

etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

Notes: Rectangle pattern

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

Notes: During certain times of the year, large tapestries of fresh flowers are installed.

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

Notes: The main gate is inscribed with "Tianxia wei gong" (天下為公) in Sun Yat-sen's calligraphy. There are other writings, such as Sun's Last Will and Testament, which were engraved throughout the Mausoleum.

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Color scheme

Notes: The Mausoleum follows the white and blue color scheme, which is particular of the Chinese Nationalist Party.

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– Yes

↳ Cult statues:

– No

↳ Statues of gods/supernatural beings:

– No

↳ Statues of humans:

– Yes

Notes: There is a 15-foot white marble statue of Sun Yat-sen sitting and other statue of Sun reclining on top of his sarcophagus.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– Yes

Notes: Reliefs depict Sun's revolutionary career.

↳ Reliefs representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Reliefs representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

Notes: There are reliefs depicting Sun Yat-sen going abroad to spread the revolution, Sun holding a baby, Sun speaking against Yuan Shi-kai, and Sun awakening the masses.

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there paintings present:

– No

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– No

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions ornamental:

– Yes

↳ Are the inscriptions informative/declarative

[e.g. historical narratives, calendars, donor lists etc...]

– Yes

Notes: There are inscriptions of Sun's ideologies such as "tianxia wei gong" (all under the heaven) and "bo ai" (universal love), an "tiandi zheng qi" (righteous in the whole world).

↳ Are the inscription a formal dedication:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Other type of decoration:

–Yes [specify]: N/A

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

Notes: The white sun on the blue sky flag of the Nationalist Party. The white sun on the blue sky surrounded by red rectangles represent the flag of the Republic of China. These symbols are part of the Nationalist China doctrine.

↳ Humans

– Yes

Notes: Statue of Sun Yat-sen sitting on a pedestal and another statue of Sun lying on top on his marble sarcophagus.

↳ Supernatural narratives

– No

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Notes: It is the burial of Sun Yat-sen.

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):

– Yes

↳ For the worship of a deified human:

– No

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:

– Yes

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:

– No

↳ Mummification:

– Yes

Notes: The Chinese government planned to preserve Sun's body in the same way as Lenin's body. The Soviet Union sent a glass-covered steel coffin to China, but it was deemed unsuitable. Sun's body was embalmed by Peking Union Medical College. It is unclear to what extent his body was preserved.

↳ Interment:

– Yes

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:

– No

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

–Other [specify]: N/A

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– Yes

Notes: Sun's body was placed in the vault of the Sacrificial Hall.

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– Yes

Notes: According to Chinese beliefs, the spirit is present where the body is buried and where the altar to the deceased is established. In this sense, one can assume that Sun's spirit is present in his mausoleum.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: tens of thousands

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: multiple times a year

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– No

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– No

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– No

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Yes

Notes: Flowers, incense

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

↳ By all the community

– Yes

Notes: The general population is expected to attend ceremonies.

↳ By specific individuals

– Yes [specify]: Political leaders

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Yes

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Yes

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

– obligatory for some

Notes: During the Republican era, the Nationalist government organized trips to the Mausoleum when the Central Executive Committee convened important meetings and when major events took place. The military, schools, and social groups frequently organized trips to the Mausoleum to pay their respects. Today high-ranking members of the Nationalist Party (KMT) make occasional pilgrimages from Taiwan.

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– No

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– No

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

Notes: During the Republican era, a special bus line was established to facilitate pilgrimage to the Mausoleum. Today since it is located up in the mountain, there is one pathway to reach it.

↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:

– Yes

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Yes

Frequency of festivals

– specify: Multiple times a year

Notes: During the Republican era, festivals were held on the New Year's Day (January 1), the anniversary of Sun's death (March 12), the National Flag day (May 5) the date of Sun Yat-sen's burial (June 1), National Day (October 10), and the anniversary of Sun's birth (November 12).

Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):

– Elites

– Non-elites

Notes: State officials and common people participate.

Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Requires special maintenance/cleansing of the place:

– No

Requires new construction/decoration of the place:

– Yes

Notes: The Mausoleum is situated in a large open space to host tens of thousands of participants. The vault where Sun's sarcophagus is located is open to the public and was built large enough to accommodate groups of visitors.

Requires maintenance/replacement of cult statue(s):

– No

On average, how many participants gather at this place:

– number: thousands

Notes: During the Republican era, on the anniversaries of Sun's birth, death, and burial, and other dates, the Nationalist officials assembled at the Mausoleum to pay respects and carry

out commemorative activities. Representatives from the military, the police force, schools, and social organizations also attended these ceremonies. In today's China, hundreds and even thousands of tourists visit the Mausoleum each day.

Is feasting part of the festival(s):

– No

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Notes: It is maintained by the Chinese government.

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:

– No

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):

– Yes

Notes: The Mausoleum was built to accommodate tens of thousands of people who were expected to attend functions such as the anniversary of the founding of the Republic of China, the anniversary of Sun Yat-sen's death, and other political gatherings. It is also part of a scenic area for tourists to visit, learn about China's history, and enjoy nature.

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):

– No

↳ Function for water management:

– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Notes: There are inscriptions of Sun's ideologies, but they are not exclusively associated with the Mausoleum.

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Sun Yat-sen Mausoleum, Musgrove, Charles. *China's Contested Capital: Architecture, Ritual, and Response in Nanjing*. Honolulu: University of Hawai'i Press, 2013.

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